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IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT PRACTICES ON QUALITY OF WORK LIFE IN SOFTWARE SECTOR (An Analysis on select units in Chennai)

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Abstract:

Information technology industry comprises on many industries such as software, BPO, ITES and hardware The need for developing managerial capabilities among managerial Software engineers such as tech leaders ,HR Managers and vice presidents they need to focus on .HRD Practices like performance appraisal, potential appraisal, training, Organization Development, performance feedback ,reward management and counseling are being designed to improve quality of work life of software employee .Such developments will grow-up where there is a HRD climate This survey used 160 senior software employees from 3 different software organizations to comment on the existence of HRD practices, prevailing HRD climate related components and the determinants of quality of work life

Key words: BPO, ITES, HRD Practices, software

INTRODUCTION:

Manpower is the ultimate resource for any organization and considered as most valuable assets to the organization also. Highly skilled oriented industries such as information technology industries manpower is essential now India is one of the biggest land of innovative entrepreneurs. Success of any organization depends on efficient and effective use of human resource in the organization .New innovative thought and skills develops in the minds of employees when the persons who enjoy their work life and job then it can be said they have good quality of work life such employees increase productivity and organizational performance. To satisfy the employee's social and psychological needs organization has to concentrate on different types of practices and these practices shows greater impact on quality of work life when there is an harmonious organizational culture.

Need for the study

Today employees are pressed and stressed due health problems, occupational problems, low employee engagement ,work overload ,strong employee monitoring , lack of work life balance, and job related issues and stress employees loosing their quality of work . so that software sector units managers or tech- leaders have to focus on not only work related aspects but also over all development and happiness of employees

Scope of the study: the present study has been taken up only in 3 software industrial organizations in Chennai

Objectives of the study

1. To present the demographic profile of the software employees
2. To examine the HRD practices in selected software industry
3. To assess the relationship between select HRD climate dimensions and HRD practices
4. To measure the quality of work life among employees
5. To offer suggestions to improve quality of work life with suitable HRD practices

Hypothesis

- 1) H_1 :There exists a relationship between HRD practices and HRD climate in select software organizations

Research methodology

Both primary and secondary data has been used for the study primary data have been collected from the sample employees in the software organization by a structured questionnaire. The secondary data gathered from journals of organizational behavior, management reviews and from doctoral theses from various universities.

The population for this study was software sector organizations in Chennai (HCL, IBM, L&T) there were 200 questionnaires were distributed to get response of employees but finally have received 160 responses. To assess the relationship between HRD practices and HRD climate have select ten HRD practices and ten variables of HRD climate. Quality of work life items of scales has been taken from Richard Walton devised 8 point criteria to determine the quality of work life

Limitations of the study:

- 1) This study has been conducted with only 160 employees and selects only 3 of the software organizations in Chennai.
- 2) This study is partial study in software sector industries
- 3) This study is only focusing on HRD practices, HRD climate variables and QWL dimensions

Review of Literature:

Rao and Abraham conducted a survey in 1986 to examine HRD climate in Indian organization. In research he found that the organization is providing average level of HRD climate and he suggest that the top management must focus on creating a harmonious healthy climate and provide appropriate HRD mechanism for the development of employees. Because employees make the organization dynamic and growth oriented.

Rao and Abraham: 1989 in their research paper entitled a study on “HRD Practices in Indian Industries: A Trend Report” they compared HRD with technological system. How a technology having structure, process like that HRD also having different kinds of process and procedures and several structures. In their research they found that all the organizations practicing recruitment training organizational development and employee counseling performance appraisals and potential appraisals but they failed to improve quality of work life of employees in many organizations where they conducted survey.

A. Sabarirajan and N.Geethanjali: 2011 their article titled as A study on quality of work life and organizational performance among the employees of public and private banks they found that there is a positive relation between QWL and employee satisfaction in both the public and private banks and they concluded that organizational performance will increase only when the human resources are satisfied with the higher quality of work life. Enhancing of QWL may be possible by improving the existing job environment.

Solkhe and choudary:2011 according to thir study hrd climate and organizational performance with focus on job satisfaction in public sector undertakings they found that for increasing better results and improved performance managers to improve welfare measres for work force and to create congenial working environment .

Amir Hussein Mohammed davoudi : 2014 in their article the study relationship between quality of work life and human resource development of teachers (saveh,iran) Findings indicated that Walton proposed eight dimensions of quality of work life are not properly considered in saveh education and he suggested that different aspects of QWL should be reviewed because all the employees should be benefited by this QWL.

Data analysis and interpretation

Table-1 Demographic profile of the employees

s.no	Demographic factors		No. of respondents	percentage
1	gender	male	115	71.87
		female	45	28.13
		total	160	100
2	age	25	50	31.25
		25-35	98	61.25
		35	12	7.5
		total	160	100
3	Marriage status	married	93	58.12
		unmarried	67	41.88
		total	160	100
4	Educational qualification	diploma	17	10.63
		intermediate	23	14.37
		Bachelor degree	66	41.25
		p.g degree	54	33.75
		total	160	100

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5	experience	5	43	26.87
		5to15years	73	45.63
		15-25	44	27.50
		total	160	100
6	Position in the org	Senior level	106	66.43
		Junior level	54	33.57
		total	160	100
7	area	urban	100	62.5
		Semi urban	60	37.5
		total	160	100
8	salary	Below 25000	50	31.25
		Btw 25000 to 50000	70	43.75
		Above 50000	40	25
		total	160	100

Table -2 a questionnaire used to survey select hrd practices in software industry. Each hrd practices are scaled on 5 point liker scale and the respondents were asked to rating the pattern is as follows

s.no	Level of agreement	ratings
1	Strongly disagree	1
2	Disagree	2
3	Sometimes agree	3
4	Often agree	4
5	Strongly agree	5

Table-3 to present the select HRD practices in software sector organization

SI. No	HRD dimensions	Mean score	Percentage(mean score-1*25)
1	Satisfied with Selection procedures	3.40	60
2	Satisfied with the Training program	3.15	53.75
3	.Performance and promotion policy in the org is good	3.65	66.25
4	Satisfied with the Transfer policy	2.96	49
5	Salary, security measures and working conditions.	3.75	68.75
6	Recreational policies good in the organization	4.06	76.5
7	We have harmonious Industrial relations.	3.44	61
8	Leaders are good in the org	2.78	44.5
9	Health facilities are good in the org	4	75
10	Supervision is good in the org	3.12	53

Significant and desirable percentage score is 60%.

In this survey it is indicated that the organization is somewhat conducting good HRD practices

Table-4 assessing the Relationship between the HRD climate and HRD Practices in Select software industry

a)Assessing HRD climate

s. no	scale	SA-(5)	AG (4)	SW A-(3)	DA (2)	SD A (1)	mean score	std
1	My organization is conducting fair selection procedure	52	78	30	0	0	4.13	0.70
2	Our company organizes Value based Induction.	28	40	15	54	23	2.97	1.36
3	Training needs are identified in our organization and providing Comprehensive training to all level employees	31	35	46	48	0	3.30	1.09
4	Our organization shaped Team based job design	36	41	34	20	29	3.21	1.40
5	Our company providing excellent Working conditions	50	40	20	35	15	3.46	1.36
6	Our organization supporting for Employee friendly Work environment	50	30	20	40	20	3.31	1.44
7	Our organization conducting employee Development oriented Performance appraisal programs	65	33	25	30	7	3.74	1.28
8	Organization is providing Compensation through a specific policy and procedure	42	64	24	15	15	3.64	1.22
9	In Our organization operational and career development plans are maintained	30	33	55	37	5	3.28	1.10
10	We are getting Value added Incentives in our organization	27	35	29	33	36	2.9	1.41
	Average frequency	41.1	42.9	29.8	31.2	15		

SA= strongly agree; AG= strongly agree; SWA= somewhat agree; DA=disagree SDA= strongly disagree

b) HRD practices

s.n o	scale	SA-(5)	AG (4)	SWA-(3)	DA (2)	SDA (1)	mean score	std
1	Our organization conducting totally fair selection procedure	55	45	35	15	10	3.75	1.19
2	We are having Value based Induction.	52	48	25	25	10	3.66	1.24
3	My organization is conducting multiple training to all levels of employees	51	43	30	21	15	3.58	1.30
4	Our organization design team based Job design	49	40	34	21	16	3.53	1.31
5	superiors supporting for our decisions	60	50	25	15	10	3.84	1.20
6	Employee friendly Work environment	55	47	28	23	7	3.75	1.19
7	Professional and personal development oriented Performance appraisal is conducting	60	54	23	18	5	3.91	1.11
8	Performance oriented hikes are proving	57	62	23	15	3	3.96	1.02
9	Recreational facilities are good in our organization	35	40	52	20	13	3.4	1.18
10	We have job security benefits in our organization	37	44	39	25	15	3.39	1.25
	Average frequency	51.1	47.3	31.4	19.8	10.4		

SA= strongly agree; AG= strongly agree; SWA= somewhat agree; DA=disagree SDA= strongly disagree

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Table-4 Assessing the relationship between HRD climate HRD practices by using Pearson correlation formula

X (HRD climate)	Y(HRD practices)	X ²	Y ²	X*Y
41.1	51.1	1689.21	2611.21	2100.21
42.9	47.3	1840.41	2237.29	2029.17
29.8	31.4	888.04	985.96	935.72
31.2	19.8	973.44	392.04	617.16
15	10.4	225	108.16	156
Σ=160	Σ=160	5616.1	6334.66	5838.86

$$N (\sum x y) - (\sum x) (\sum y)$$

Pearson correlation coefficient factor = r=-----

$$\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2] (n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}$$

$$5 \times 5838.86 - 25600$$

$$r = \frac{5 \times 5838.86 - 25600}{\sqrt{(5 \times 5616.1 - 25600) \times (5 \times 6334.66 - 25600)}} = 0.926$$

$$\sqrt{(5 \times 5616.1 - 25600) \times (5 \times 6334.66 - 25600)}$$

The result indicates that there is a strong positive relationship between HRD practices and HRD climate determinants. the value of r is 0.926.this is a strong positive correlation, the value of r², the coefficient determination is 0.8575. the p value is 0.023895. the result is significant at P<0.05

Table -5 To measure the quality of work life among employees

s. no	scale	SA-5	AG-4	SW A-3	DA -2	SDA -1	mean score	std	%
1	I am getting Fair compensation in relation to cost of living , ability and incentives	34	36	33	37	20	3.16	1.33	54
2	My organization is providing safe and healthy working conditions	39	45	33	23	20	3.37	1.32	59.25
3	I have opportunity to use and develop my skills	41	39	49	12	19	3.44	1.27	61
4	I am having growth in the organization and job security	49	53	25	10	23	3.59	1.35	64.75
5	We work Collectively in the organization that increase social integration	40	62	38	20	0	3.76	0.96	69
6	My supervisors supported and suggested me to do work in new ways in the work organization that increase confidence in me	39	49	40	22	10	3.53	1.77	63.25
7	I am able to handling work and family life balance	20	40	40	40	20	3	1.22	50
8	My organization providing awarding and rewarding on performance	50	57	47	6	0	3.94	0.86	73
	Average frequency								

SA= strongly agree; AG= strongly agree; SWA= somewhat agree; DA=disagree SDA= strongly disagree

Findings

Objective -1 finding

71.87% of employees are male and 28.13 % of the employees are female.31.25% of the respondent's age is equal or below 25 years, 61.25% of the respondents are is between 25 to 35 years, 7.5% of the respondents' age is above 35 years. 58.12% of the employees are married, 41.88% are UN married. 10.63% are having educational qualification as diploma, 14.37% are intermediate, 41.25 are bachelor degree and 33.75% are pg degree.

26.87% are having 5 years of experience,45.63% of the employees having 5 to 15 years of experience and 27.50% are having 15 to 25 years of experience.66.43% of the employees are senior level positioning in the organization.33.57% of the employees are having junior level positioning in the organization.

62.5% of employees are from urban areas and 37.5% of the employees are from semi urban areas.31.25% of the employees getting below 25000 salary,43.75% of the employees earning 25000 to 50000 and 25% of the employees are getting salaries above 50000 rupees per month as basic salary

Objective -2 findings

In this study it is indicated that the organization is somewhat conducting good HRD practices

Objective -3 findings

The result indicates that there is a **strong positive relationship between HRD practices and HRD climate** determinants. The value of r is 0.926.this is a strong positive correlation, the value of r^2 , the co efficient determination is 0.8575. The p value is 0.023895. The result is significant at $P < 0.05$ so the hypothesis must accepted

Objective -4 findings

54% of employees getting Fair compensation in relation to cost of living, ability and incentives 59.25% of employees said that their organization is providing safe and healthy working conditions to their employees.61% of the employees said they are having the opportunity to use and develop their skills64.75% of the employees are having growth in the organization and job security69% of the employees said they work collectively in the organization that increase social integration.63.25% of the employees said that their supervisors supported and suggested to do work in new ways in the work organization that increase confidence .50% of the employees said that they are able to handling work and family life balance.73% of the employees said that the organization providing awarding and rewarding on performance

Suggestions

- ✓ Salary hikes must provide according to the changes
- ✓ Performance appraisal program should be done on the basis of 360 degree appraisal
- ✓ Training program should designed to all levels and to all categories of employees

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- ✓ Stress removal programs should be designed in the organization
- ✓ Employees counseling's must be conducted in the organization frequently
- ✓ Flexi working system will reduce burden on employees
- ✓ Redesign of HRD subsystems in the organization encourage self development of employees
- ✓ Providing meaningful work through proper open communicating and meetings with employees

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